

Notes on Contributors

Luminița HOARȚĂ CĂRĂUȘU: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Professor, Romanian Language and General Linguistics Department, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, Romania; 3) author of 12 books, 2 courses of lectures, 63 articles and investigations published in Romania and abroad; 4) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 5) member of national and international research teams and associations; 6) member of Honorary Board of *Speech and Context* Journal; 7) led a series of courses in a number of prestigious universities from Germany: Konstanz University, Des Saarlandes University (Saarbruecken), Friedrich Schiller University (Jena) etc.; 8) guides doctoral theses; 9) manager of research projects (*Pragmatics of Pronoun, A Corpus of Contemporary Spoken Romanian* etc.); 10) member of the research teams within some projects (*Colloquial language in Romance area. A Pragmalinguistic Synchronic and Diachronic Study*); 11) organizer of scientific conferences; 12) member of the Defense Board of Doctoral Theses; 13) research areas: syntax and morphology of Romanian, linguistic pragmatics, persuasive strategies in political and publicistic discourses.

Ligia GHILEA: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Lecturer, Gheorghe Dima Music Academy, Cluj-Napoca, Romania; 3) author of scientific and didactic works, published in Romania and abroad; 4) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 5) research areas: musics, music theory.

Ion GUȚU: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, Moldova State University; 3) author of scientific and didactic works, published in Moldova and abroad; 4) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 5) adviser of doctoral theses in Romance philology; 6) member of the Scientific Specialization Seminar and Council for the Defense of the Doctoral Theses, speciality 10.02.05 – Romance languages (Moldova State University); 7) member of national and international research associations; 8) research areas: French linguistics, literary semiotics, sociolinguistics.

Lilia RĂCIULA: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Senior lecturer, Romanian Language Department, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți, Republic of Moldova; 3) participant in national and international scientific conferences and seminars; 4) author of 25 scientific works; 5) member of Scientific Board of *Glottodidactica* Journal; 6) research areas: Romanian philology, literary semiotics.

Valentina ȘMATOV: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți, Republic of Moldova; 3) author of scientific and didactic works, published in Moldova and abroad; 4) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 5) member of Scientific Board of *Speech and Context* Journal; 6) led a series of courses in a number of prestigious universities from USA; 7) research areas: British and American linguistics, text linguistics, discourse theory.

Mihail RUMLEANSCHI: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți, Republic of Moldova; 3) author of scientific and didactic works, published in Moldova and abroad; 4) participant and organizer of national and international scientific conferences; 5) member of Scientific Board of *Glottodidactica* Journal; 6) led a series of courses in a number of prestigious universities from Russia and France; 7) research areas: French linguistics, text linguistics, speech linguistics, French and Francophone civilisations.

Angela COȘCIUG: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, French Philology Department, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți; 3) member of the Scientific Specialization Seminar for the Defense of the Doctoral Theses, speciality 10.02.05 – Romance languages (Moldova State University); 4) member of the Scientific Specialization Council for the Defense of the Doctoral Theses, speciality 10.02.05 – Romance languages (Moldova State University); 5) scientific adviser (since 2010) and reviewer of doctoral theses in Romance philology, national expert of textbooks of French for pre-university establishments from the Republic of Moldova; 6) since 2007, post-doctoral studies, Moldova State University; 7) author of 70 scientific and didactic works (monographs, essays, studies, textbooks, guides, courses of lectures, articles, abstracts) published in prestigious national and international journals and volumes (in Moldova, Romania, Russia, Canada, Albania etc.); 8) organizer of scientific conferences; 9) publisher of scientific national and international conference volumes; 10) participant in 80 national and international scientific conferences; 11) editor-in-chief of *Speech and Context* International Journal of Linguistics, Semiotics and Literary Science; editor-in-chief of *Glottodidactica* Biannual Journal of Applied Linguistics; 12) member of the Scientific Board of *Мова та Історія/Language and History* Journal published at Taras Șevcenko National University of Kiev, Ukraine, of the Scientific Board of *Communication Interculturelle et Littérature/Intercultural Communication and Literature* Journal published at Dunărea de Jos University of Galați, Romania and of the Scientific Board of *Concordia Discors vs Discordia Concors* Journal published at

Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava, Romania; 13) Grant of the French Government (2007); 14) research areas: Romance linguistics, general semiotics, literary semiotics, discourse theory, specialized French Language, translation studies, Francophone literature, Applied Linguistics, Contrastive linguistics.

Ioana-Iulia OLARU: 1) Ph.D. Student; 2) Lecturer of Art History Department, Faculty of Arts, Ornamental Crafts and Design of George Enescu State University of Iași; 3) member of „The Research Center of Aesthetic and Artistic Creation” of the Faculty of Arts, Ornamental Crafts and Design of George Enescu State University of Iași; 4) author of 35 scientific works (articles), published in national and international journals (in Romania, Moldova); 5) participant in 7 national and international scientific conferences; 6) co-editor of *The Research Center of Aesthetic and Artistic Creation* Journal, Faculty of Arts, Ornamental Crafts and Design, George Enescu State University of Iași; 7) co-editor of doctoral students Journal, Faculty of Arts, Ornamental Crafts and Design, George Enescu State University of Iași; 8) co-editor of *Alloquor* Journal, Department of Romanian Language for foreign students, Faculty of Philology, A.I. Cuza State University of Iași; 9) research areas: universal art history, Romanian art history.

Rahim OMBASHI: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, Fan S. Noli State University, Korça, Albania; 3) author of scientific and didactic works, published in Albania and abroad; 4) participant and organizer of national and international scientific conferences; 5) research areas: Albanian literature.

Irina CIORNAIA: 1) Lecturer, German Philology Department, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți; 2) author of scientific works published in prestigious national and international journals and volumes; 3) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 4) winner of several grants offered by universities from Germany and Austria; 5) research areas: German literature, comparative literature.

Virginia POPOVIĆ: 1) Assistant Professor, Novi Sad University, Serbia; 2) author of scientific works; 3) participant in scientific conferences; 4) research areas: Contrastive linguistics.

Marina TETERINA: 1) Lecturer, English Philology Department, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți; 2) author of scientific works published in prestigious national and international journals and volumes; 3) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 4) research areas: British and American linguistics, contrastive linguistics, cognitive linguistics.

Viorica CONDRAT: 1) MA; 2) Ph.D. student; 3) lecturer, English Philology Department, “Alecu Russo” State University of Bălți; 4) author of scientific works published in prestigious national and international journals and volumes; 5) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 6) research areas: British and American literature, comparative literature.

Daniela VLADU: 1) Assistant Professor, Babeș-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania; 2) author of scientific works published in prestigious national and international journals and volumes; 3) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 4) research areas: contrastive linguistics, translation.

Georgiana Elisabeta PANAIT: 1) teacher of Romanian Language and Literature, Buzău, Romania; 2) author of poems, published in prestigious literary journals.

Veronica PĂCURARU: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, Moldova State University; 3) author of scientific and didactic works, published in Moldova and abroad; 4) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 5) adviser of doctoral theses in Romance philology; 6) member of the Scientific Specialization Seminar and Council for the Defense of the Doctoral Theses, speciality 10.02.05 – Romance languages (Moldova State University); 7) research areas: French linguistics, sociolinguistics.